

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In reply refer to:
2022-0069210-S7-001

December 19, 2022

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Office of Wastewater Management
U.S. Environmental Protection Agency
Washington, D.C. 20460

Subject: Formal Section 7 Consultation on the Santa Clara Valley Water District's Sunnyvale East and Sunnyvale West Channels Flood Protection Project

Dear Ms. McCurdy:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) July 28, 2022, request for initiation of informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Santa Clara Valley Water District's Sunnyvale East and Sunnyvale West Channels Flood Protection Project (proposed project) in the City of Sunnyvale, Santa Clara County, California. The EPA determined the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the federally endangered California least tern (*Sterna antillarum browni*), endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)¹. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR § 402).

On July 5, 2022, the U.S. District Court of the Northern District Court of California vacated the 2019 regulations implementing section 7 of the Act. On September 21, 2022, the Ninth Circuit Court of Appeals granted a request to stay the U.S. District Court of Northern California's July 5, 2022, order that vacated the 2019 Act regulations. On November 14, 2022, the U.S. District Court of Northern California granted a motion for remand without vacatur for the 2019 Act regulations. As a result, the 2019 regulations are again in effect, and the Service has relied upon

¹ Until the Service officially adopts recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union to Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence. Note, the change in taxonomic assignment does not change the listing status of the species.

the 2019 regulations in rendering this biological opinion. However, because the outcome of the legal challenges to 2019 Act Regulations is still unknown, we considered whether our substantive analyses and conclusions in this consultation would have been different if the pre-2019 regulations were applied. Our analysis included the prior definition of "effects of the action," among other prior terms and provisions. We considered all the "direct and indirect effects" and the "interrelated and interdependent activities" when determining the "effects of the action." As a result, we determined the substantive analysis and conclusions would have been the same, irrespective of which regulations applied.

On July 5, 2022, the U.S. District Court of the Northern District Court of California vacated the 2019 regulations implementing section 7 of the Act. On September 21, 2022, the Ninth Circuit Court of Appeals granted a request to stay the U.S. District Court of Northern California's July 5, 2022, order that vacated the 2019 Act regulations. On November 14, 2022, the U.S. District Court of Northern California granted a motion for remand without vacatur for the 2019 Act regulations. As a result, the 2019 regulations are again in effect, and the Service has relied upon the 2019 regulations in issuing our written concurrence on the action agency's "may affect, not-likely-to-adversely-affect" determination. However, because the outcome of the legal challenges to the 2019 Act regulations is still unknown, we considered whether our substantive analyses and conclusions would have been different if the pre-2019 regulations were applied in this informal consultation. Our analysis included the prior definition of "effects of the action." We considered all the "direct and indirect effects" and the "interrelated and interdependent activities" when determining the "effects of the action." We then considered whether any "effects of the action" that overlap with applicable ranges of listed species would be wholly beneficial, insignificant, or discountable to the species. As a result, we determined the substantive analysis and conclusions would have been the same, irrespective of which regulations applied.

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the EPA's issuance of financial assistance to the Santa Clara Valley Water District under the Water Infrastructure Finance and Innovation Act for the proposed project.

In reviewing this proposed project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the EPA's July 28, 2022, letter requesting consultation and enclosures; (2) emails between the EPA, Service, Santa Clara Valley Water District, and consultants; (3) the October 2013 Draft Environmental Impact Report (Horizon Water and Environment, LLC. 2013) and the August 2014 Final Environmental Impact Report (Horizon Water and Environment, LLC. 2014); and (4) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California least tern. The Action Area does not contain suitable nesting habitat. Although rare, terns have been observed foraging in Pond A4 but the wastewater treatment ponds and Sunnyvale East and West Channels are not considered preferred foraging habitat. Disturbance from construction activity may temporarily deter terns from foraging near the Action Area but is not anticipated to result in adverse effects given the availability of foraging habitat in South San Francisco Bay.

However, the Service does not concur with the EPA's determination that the proposed project is

not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail due to potential effects to individuals from noise disturbance. Therefore, the remainder of this document is the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

Consultation History

- July 29, 2022 The Service's Sacramento Fish and Wildlife office forwarded the EPA's July 28, 2022 email consultation initiation request to the Service's San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office.
- September 2, 2022 The Service sent an email requesting additional information from the EPA regarding the project description and species effects.
- September 28, 2022 The Service received additional information in an email from the EPA.
- October 6, 2022 The Service sent an email to the EPA requesting clarification and information as it relates specifically to consultation not the California Environmental Quality Act (CEQA) documents.
- October 12-14, 2022 The Service and EPA exchanged emails regarding CEQA documents and similarity between this and a previous City of Sunnyvale project funded by the EPA (Service file number 08FBDT00-2020-F-0111).
- October 20, 2022 The Santa Clara Valley Water District emailed the Service additional information specific to project components near habitat.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Sunnyvale Channels flow northward through the City of Sunnyvale. The far southern portion of the Sunnyvale East Channel is contained in an underground pipe and located in the northern area of the City of Cupertino. At the northern end of the proposed project area, toward San Francisco Bay, the channels discharge to the Guadalupe Slough adjacent to Pond A4. In the northern (downstream) reaches of the channels near San Francisco Bay, the channels receive tidal backwatering via the Guadalupe Slough and can also receive excess flows from nearby Calabazas and San Tomas Aquino Creeks.

The proposed project upgrades approximately 6.4 miles of the Sunnyvale East Channel and approximately three miles of the Sunnyvale West Channel. The goal of the proposed project is to provide 1% (100-year) flood protection to Sunnyvale residents, schools, and businesses. The proposed improvements include bridge/culvert improvements, channel improvements, levee

modifications, installation of floodwalls, and maintenance road/trail modifications. Activities within the interior of the City of Sunnyvale are not expected to result in adverse effects to listed species and will not be discussed further. The remainder of the section will more specifically describe activities within or near habitat.

Caribbean Drive Bridge Replacement

On the East Channel at Caribbean Drive, the existing dual-span bridge would be completely replaced with a reinforced concrete, triple-cell box culvert bridge. The existing dual span bridge on concrete piers would be removed and the piers left in place below the sub-grade of the proposed triple-cell culvert. Shoring would be installed during removal of the existing bridge, consistent with applicable safety standards and requirements, to protect the abutment, existing roadway, and channel. During work within the channel, temporary cofferdams would be installed within the channel both upstream and downstream. Compared with the existing bridge structure, the new culvert structure would extend an additional 8 feet in length on the upstream and downstream sides. This additional 8 feet on both sides is requested by the City of Sunnyvale (the City) for public safety with the installation of future public sidewalks along Caribbean Drive. The new culvert would be installed approximately 2 to 3 feet deeper than the existing channel invert in order to accommodate tidal sediment deposition of bay muds. The hydraulic model accounted for this sediment deposition of bay muds within the triple cell culvert, including 2-foot of future sea level rise. The reconstructed channel profile would mimic the existing profile.

Construction of this triple cell box culvert would be phased over the proposed project's two-year construction period. The north span of the roadway would be installed during the first year of the in-channel construction period and the south span of the roadway would be constructed during the second in-channel construction season. It is estimated that construction of the new bridge culvert and wingwalls would take a total of 180 working days, phased over two years with a 12-person crew. Equipment for construction would include: an excavator dump trucks, front end loader, water truck, flatbed boom truck, concrete truck, crane, vibratory roller, and air hoses and compressor.

Carl Road Box Culvert Replacement

The existing reinforced concrete box culvert at Carl Road, located on the West Channel, would be completely replaced with a new single-cell, reinforced concrete box culvert. The new box culvert would be 10-foot by 15-foot and would completely replace the existing 9-foot by 10-foot culvert. The bottom of the existing box culvert is assumed, for hydraulic modeling purposes, to be buried with approximately 3 feet of channel bed sediment due to tidal flows. The new box culvert would be buried so that its bed elevation would not be higher than the bottom elevation of the wingwalls at the Caribbean Drive culvert located upstream. A temporary cofferdam would be installed in the channel both upstream and downstream to facilitate culvert replacement.

Construction of the new culvert would take place during one of the two in-channel construction periods. It is estimated that construction of the new bridge culvert would take a total of 90 working days with a 10-person crew.

Channel Excavation and Regrading

Regrading of the existing channel is proposed for one location in the West Channel and no regrading would occur within the East Channel. Approximately 500 linear feet would be regraded from Carl Road to Caribbean Drive. Regrading at this location would allow for increased channel capacity to accommodate high flows during a 100-year storm and compliance with freeboard minimum height requirements by the Federal Emergency Management Agency and Santa Clara Valley Water District. Regrading would lower the channel invert elevation by approximately four feet to restore the as-built channel invert profile. Channel banks would be graded to a 2:1 slope for stability. Adjacent levee enlargement would take place concurrently, discussed below.

During work within the channel, temporary cofferdams would be installed in the channel. Installation of the cofferdams would likely be coordinated with this work and the adjacent Carl Road box culvert replacement. The estimated schedule to complete this work is approximately 20 working days with a 10-person crew, including the channel excavation and regrading as well as the levee enlargement. Construction equipment would include: an excavator, dump trucks, front end loader, tractor/dozer, and water truck.

Levee Raising

Existing levees would be raised at two locations to provide a 100-year level of flood protection. Levees would be increased in height for approximately 500 linear feet of the West Channel south of Pond A4 and immediately east of the City's Water Pollution Control Plant (WPCP) and along the East Channel beginning at the confluence with Guadalupe Slough and extending approximately 1,150 linear feet. Levees would be raised between approximately 2 to 5.5 feet by placement of earthen fill, thereby reducing the floodwall heights at these two locations. The fill would be compacted to 95 percent relative maximum density. All levee side slopes would be graded to an approximate 2:1 slope for stability. The top surface of the levees would be surfaced with new aggregate base rock and would continue to serve as a maintenance road used by multiple agencies, including but not limited to Santa Clara Valley Water District, the City, Pacific Gas & Electric, and others. American Disability Act compliant sloped levee ramps would also be constructed and aggregate base reinstalled to allow maintenance vehicle and pedestrian trail access onto the raised levees.

Estimated timeframe for this work is approximately 30 working days with a 10-person crew, anticipating 25 working days on the East Channel and 5 working days on the West Channel. Construction equipment would include: a front end loader, grader, tractor/dozer, vibratory roller with blade, and water truck. Road restoration would include: double bottom dump trucks, grader, tractor/dozer, front end loader, vibratory roller, water truck, dump trucks, asphalt concrete paver,

drum rollers, flatbed truck, concrete trucks, air hoses and compressor, and traffic control message boards.

Levee Enlargement

Existing levees would be enlarged along the West Channel between Carl Road and Caribbean Drive, along both the east and west banks. The proposed project incorporates channel and levee enlargement at this location (rather than floodwalls) to provide adequate flood protection and allow wildlife ingress-egress and minimize impacts to burrowing owl and other wildlife which utilize the existing former landfill area adjacent to this section of the West Channel. The levee enlargement would involve increasing the existing vertical levee height of both levees by approximately 5-6 feet, lowering the channel invert elevation by four feet to restore the channel invert to the as-built channel invert elevation, and widening the east and west levees outward to accommodate public Bay Trail access (west bank) and a 12-foot wide emergency vehicle access roadway (east bank), as required by the City. The levees would be enlarged with the placement of earthen fill and levee sides would be graded to an approximate 2:1 slope for channel slope stability. The top surface of the levees would be surfaced with new aggregate base rock and would serve as a channel maintenance/access road. The levee surface/maintenance road along the east bank, between Carl Road and Caribbean Drive, would serve as a permanent emergency access route for the adjacent landfill and the WPCP.

The estimated timeframe to complete this work is approximately 20 working days with a 10-person crew. Construction equipment would include: a front end loader, grader, tractor/dozer, vibratory roller with blade, and water truck. Road restoration would include: double bottom dump trucks, grader, tractor/dozer, front end loader, vibratory roller, water truck, dump trucks, asphalt concrete paver, drum rollers, flatbed truck, concrete trucks, air hoses and compressor, and traffic control message boards.

Floodwalls

Floodwalls with the following configurations would be installed on the East and West Channels:

- East Channel, confluence with Guadalupe Slough to Caribbean Drive: Floodwalls 3 to 7 feet in height would be installed outboard on both banks. Immediately downstream of Caribbean Drive, floodwalls would be 8 feet in height with inboard and outboard configurations.
- West Channel, near confluence with Guadalupe Slough to Carl Road: Inboard and outboard floodwalls generally 4 to 5 feet in height and 7 feet immediately downstream of Carl Road would be installed.
- West Channel between Carl Road and Caribbean Drive: Inboard floodwalls approximately 8 feet in height would be installed on both banks to the raised levees between Carl Road and Caribbean Drive.

Floodwall ramps would be constructed at several locations where floodwalls meet bridge/culvert

wingwalls. The purpose of the ramps is to provide maintenance road access and pedestrian trail access at road crossings.

Along the East Channel, it is anticipated that it would take a 10-person crew approximately 20 working days to excavate soil for the construction of floodwalls. It would take approximately 50 working days to construct the floodwalls and ramp retaining walls, including forming, reinforcement, and placement of concrete. Along the West Channel, it is anticipated that it would take a 10-person crew approximately 30 working days to excavate soil for the construction of floodwalls. It would take approximately 80 working days to construct the floodwalls and ramp retaining walls, including forming, reinforcement, and placement of concrete. Construction equipment would include: an excavator, dump trucks, front end loader, water truck, flatbed boom truck, concrete trucks, vibratory roller, and air hoses and compressor.

Maintenance Road Improvements

Aggregate base maintenance roads are present atop both levees downstream of Caribbean Drive on the East Channel and downstream of Carl Road on the West Channel. Earthen maintenance roads are present atop both levees from Carl Road upstream to Caribbean Drive. The proposed project proposes to reconfigure these existing maintenance roads with a 10-foot section of asphalt concrete trail with 2-foot aggregate base shoulders along both the West Channel and East Channels in accordance with the agreements executed between Santa Clara Valley Water District and the City.

It is anticipated that it would take approximately 20 working days to resurface the maintenance road along the East Channel with a 10-person crew and 20 working days to resurface the maintenance roads along the West Channel. Construction equipment would include: double bottom dump trucks, grader, tractor/dozer, front end loader, vibratory roller, water truck, dump trucks, asphalt concrete paver, drum rollers, flatbed truck, concrete trucks, and air hoses and compressor.

Construction Timing

Replacement of the Caribbean Drive Bridge, Carl Road culvert, and channel excavation and Regrading would be constrained to the in-channel work window granted by the Corps, California Department of Fish and Wildlife, and San Francisco Bay Regional Water Quality Control Board in the proposed project's permits respectively. The in-channel work window is likely to encompass June through October. Levee modifications, floodwall construction, and maintenance road improvements would not be constrained to the in-channel work window.

Conservation Measures

1. *BIO-4: Minimize Access Impacts.* The use of existing channel access points is required, if feasible, in order to minimize impacts on marsh and aquatic habitats and listed species that occupy them. If temporary access points must be constructed, they will be created as

close to the work area as possible to minimize running equipment in waterways and the potential associated adverse effects on water quality.

2. *WQ-1: Conduct Work from the Top of Bank.* For in-channel minor work activities, work will be conducted from the top of the bank if access is available and there are flows in the channel, minimizing potential water-quality impacts.
3. *WQ-2: Evaluate Use of Wheel and Track Mounted Vehicles in Stream Bottoms.* Field personnel will use the appropriate equipment for the job that minimizes disturbance to the stream bottom. This Best Management Practice (BMP) will thus minimize the potential for in-channel work to compact the substrate, potentially killing benthic invertebrates (which may serve as prey for California clapper rails) and otherwise altering marsh and aquatic habitat.
4. *WQ-4: Handle Sediments so as to Minimize Water Quality Impacts.* Requires truck beds to be lined with an impervious material or the tailgate to be blocked with appropriate filtration material when hauling sediment-laden water. This BMP will thus minimize the potential for sediment-laden water to enter waterbodies occupied by listed species, which could result in the degradation of marsh and aquatic habitat for California clapper rails, California least terns, and salt marsh harvest mice.
5. *WQ-5: Avoid Runoff from Soil Stockpiles.* If soil is to be stockpiled, no run-off will be allowed to flow to a creek, thus minimizing the potential for increased sediment deposition in waterbodies to result in the degradation of marsh and aquatic habitat for California clapper rails, California least terns, and salt marsh harvest mice.
6. *WQ-7: Prevent Erosion Downstream of Bank Protection Sites.* Requires bank stabilization designs to incorporate proactive protection of areas vulnerable to erosion, thereby minimizing the potential for increased sediment deposition in waterbodies to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work sites.
7. *WQ-9: Minimize Local Erosion Increase from In-channel Vegetation Removal.* Requires the potential effect of localized erosion to be minimized by leaving vegetation at the toe of the bank to the maximum extent possible, thereby minimizing the potential for increased sediment deposition in waterbodies to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work sites.
8. *WQ-14: Use Temporary Seeding for Erosion Control as Appropriate.* For banks that are scraped, an erosion control seed mix will be used. Temporary earthen access roads will be seeded when site and horticultural conditions are suitable. This BMP will minimize the potential for increased erosion and sediment deposition in waterbodies to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work sites.
9. *WQ-16: Avoid Erosion When Restoring Flows.* This BMP requires flows to be restored to temporarily dewatered areas in a manner that minimizes erosion in order to minimize the

potential for increased scour and sediment deposition in waterbodies to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work sites.

10. *WQ-21: Control Sediment/ Turbidity for Discharges Less than 50 Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTUs)*. To control sediment and turbidity in discharges from the proposed project activities where the source is treated water, recycled water, raw water, or groundwater with a turbidity of less than 50 NTU, this BMP requires the discharge to be characterized so that the appropriate option for discharge can be selected and requires the use of appropriate control measures when discharging water. This BMP will minimize the potential for sediment deposition in waterbodies to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work sites.
11. *WQ-22: Control Sediment/Turbidity for Discharge Greater than 50 NTU*. To control sediment and turbidity in discharges from Project activities where the source is treated water, recycled water, raw water, or groundwater with a turbidity of greater than 50 NTU, this BMP requires the discharge to be characterized so that the appropriate option for discharge can be selected. This BMP requires the use of appropriate control measures and the inspection and maintenance of control measures when discharging water, thus, minimizing the potential for sediment deposition in waterbodies to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work.
12. *WQ-40: Prevent Water Pollution*. Oily, greasy, or sediment laden substances or other material that originate from Project operations and may degrade the quality of surface water or adversely affect aquatic life, fish, or wildlife will not be allowed to enter, or be placed where they may later enter, any waterway. Further, the proposed project will take all necessary precautions to limit the increase in turbidity of any watercourse flowing past the construction site. This BMP will minimize the potential for increased turbidity to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work.
13. *WQ-41: Prevent Stormwater Pollution*. This BMP requires the implementation of suitable erosion control, sediment control, source control, treatment control, material management, and non- stormwater management BMPs consistent with the latest edition of the California Stormwater Quality Association Stormwater Best Management Practices Handbook. This BMP will minimize the potential for increased turbidity to result in the degradation of marsh or aquatic habitats downstream from work.
14. *HM-9: Clean Vehicles and Equipment*. This BMP requires equipment to be cleaned of any visible sediment or vegetation clumps before transferring and using in a different watershed to avoid spreading pathogens or exotic/invasive species that could adversely affect listed species or degrade their habitat.
15. *HM-10: Assure Proper Vehicle and Equipment Fueling*. This BMP requires fueling of vehicles or equipment to occur outside the channel and immediate floodplain, if feasible, and requires all fueling sites to have a secondary containment system to minimize the potential for fuel leaks or spills to occur in, or spread into, habitat occupied by listed

species, degrading habitat quality and potentially killing California clapper rails, least terns, salt marsh harvest mice, or their food.

16. *HM-11: Assure Proper Vehicle and Equipment Maintenance.* This BMP requires the regular inspection and maintenance of vehicles to prevent or repair leaks, prior to use; the creek channel or immediate floodplain, unless equipment stationed in these locations cannot be readily relocated; and, if necessary, requires all servicing of equipment done at the job site to be conducted in a designated, protected area. This BMP will minimize the potential for fuel leaks to occur in, or spread into, habitat occupied by listed species, degrading the habitat and potentially killing California clapper rails, least terns, salt marsh harvest mice, or their food.
17. *HM-12: Assure Proper Hazardous Materials Management.* This BMP requires measures to be implemented to ensure that hazardous materials are properly handled and the quality of water resources is protected by all reasonable means to minimize the potential for hazardous materials to contaminate habitat occupied by listed species, degrading the habitat and potentially killing California clapper rails, least terns, salt marsh harvest mice, or their food.
18. *HM-13: Prevent Spills.* Leaks and spills of fuels, lubricants, and other fluids from heavy equipment could injure or kill California clapper rails, least terns, salt marsh harvest mice, or their food. This BMP will minimize the potential for this adverse effect by requiring field personnel to be appropriately trained in spill prevention, hazardous material control, and clean-up of accidental spills and prohibiting the fueling, repair, cleaning, maintenance, or washing of vehicles in a creek channel or in areas at the top of a channel bank that may flow into a creek channel.
19. To avoid the loss of individual California clapper rails and salt marsh harvest mice, activities within or adjacent to California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse habitat (i.e., tidal brackish marsh) will not occur within two hours before or after extreme high tides (8.62 feet or above, as measured at Palo Alto Yacht Harbor 9414525 gage using Mean Lower Low Water datum), when the marsh plain is inundated. This measure is appropriate because protective cover for California clapper rails and salt marsh harvest mice is limited and construction activities could disturb individuals and prevent them from reaching available cover.
20. During levee raising activities along the south/east bank of the East Channel near its confluence with Guadalupe Slough, starting at the eastern edge of the Twin Creeks Sports Complex and continuing eastward, a minimum 10-foot buffer, measured as the straight-line distance (e.g., diagonally/down-slope on a sloped bank), will be maintained between the outer limits of proposed project construction activities (i.e., silt fence installation) and any marsh habitat present beyond the proposed project site boundary (i.e., in the wetland mitigation area to the south or along Guadalupe Slough to the north in Sunnyvale Baylands Park/Sunnyvale Baylands Seasonal Wetland Preserve). In addition, proposed

project personnel will ensure that the silt fencing in this area is sturdy and is regularly maintained so that no material falls into these wetlands during levee raising.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, lighting, or movement associated with the proposed project. The project proponent quantified the entire project boundary but did not separate the specific areas that may affect species for this consultation. As such, the Action Area includes the entire Sunnyvale West Channel project boundary (33.36 acres), the entire Sunnyvale East Channel project boundary (66.50 acres), the adjacent Moffatt Slough and Guadalupe Slough marshes, and within the areas of noise disturbance. The Service estimates the total Action Area to be approximately 100 acres with an additional 800 feet extending into marsh areas and adjacent Sunnyvale Baylands Seasonal Wetland Preserve.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably will be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the *Status of the Species*, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of Species

California Clapper Rail

Information about the California clapper rail biology and ecology is available in the Recovery

Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. Information about the salt marsh harvest mouse biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3630.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal Projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The Sunnyvale Channels flow northward through the City of Sunnyvale. The far southern portion of the East Channel is contained in an underground pipe and located in the northern area of the City of Cupertino. At the northern end of the proposed project Area, toward San Francisco Bay, the channels discharge to the Guadalupe Slough adjacent to Pond A4. In the northern (downstream) reaches of the channels near San Francisco Bay, the channels receive tidal backwatering via the Guadalupe Slough and can also receive excess flows from nearby Calabazas and San Tomas Aquino Creeks.

The Sunnyvale Channels primarily traverse and collect stormwater runoff from developed and urban areas. The channels are generally trapezoidal, with earthen embankments. Several reaches have hardened concrete or rock sloped banks, and many sections are subsurface concrete box

culverts, primarily at road crossings. The channels are generally bounded by 10- to 20-feet of right-of-way that runs parallel along both banks of the channels. Such right-of-way typically contains District maintenance roads and/or undeveloped areas and buffer the channels from adjacent land uses. The Sunnyvale Channels cross major arterial roadways, including U.S. Highway 101, State Route 237, Caribbean Drive, Central Expressway, and El Camino Real, as well as numerous smaller, local roadways. In the northern Project Area, development density is less intense, consisting of baylands that fringe San Francisco Bay. This area is characterized by open spaces in the vicinity of Guadalupe Slough and Pond A4, with higher natural resource value.

The Sunnyvale West Channel is a linear, channelized drainage feature that has full tidal influence from the similar but much larger Moffett Channel, which connects to Guadalupe Slough and drains to San Francisco Bay. Open water portions of the Sunnyvale West Channel receive freshwater inputs from precipitation, stormwater and irrigation runoff, and effluent from the WPCP.

The Sunnyvale East Channel is an open-water channel that extends approximately 6.5 miles from Junipero Serra Channel downstream to Guadalupe Slough. It is adjacent to the Twin Creeks Sports Complex and the Sunnyvale Baylands Seasonal Wetland Preserve (a 105-acre wetland preserve owned by the County of Santa Clara, which includes a 3.0-acre seasonal wetland restoration site, a 3.6-acre freshwater restoration site, and a 5.5-acre pickleweed habitat restoration site for the salt marsh harvest mouse) near its confluence with Guadalupe Slough.

Pond A4 and the WPCP water treatment ponds occur immediately adjacent and in between both channels. Pond A4 is an open-water salt pond that is currently not tidally influenced. The pond is managed by operation of a pump located at its southeast corner. Pond A4 is characterized by a large area of open water, floating algae, and a series of islands that run parallel to the southern edge of the pond.

The northern reaches of both the Sunnyvale Channels are tidally influenced by hydrologic connection with Guadalupe Slough. The East Channel connects directly with Guadalupe Slough, while the West Channel connects indirectly via the Moffett Channel. The approximate extent of tidal influence is the State Route 237 crossing of the East Channel and the Mathilda Avenue crossing of the West Channel. However, the majority of marsh in these tidal zones is freshwater marsh, and only the lowermost reach of the East Channel and the lower portion of Moffett Channel support tidal brackish marsh.

The tidal brackish marshes are limited in extent and highly disturbed. They are located adjacent to maintenance roads where moderate levels of human disturbance (e.g., from vehicles and pedestrians) occur regularly. In addition, maintenance activities conducted by the Santa Clara Valley Water District have reduced the amount of vegetative cover present in this habitat type.

The project proponent provided the Draft Environmental Impact Report noise analysis for the surrounding developed areas. They did not analyze noise impacts for the Bay-side marsh environment. The existing ambient noise along the Sunnyvale Channels ranged from 50-74 dBA

Day-Night Level. Existing operations and maintenance of the WPCP and Sunnyvale Channels and human activity near the Sunnyvale Channels provide a baseline level of disturbance. The Service assumes ambient noise levels are in the lower range in the tidal marsh areas in Moffatt and Guadalupe Channels.

The Service issued a biological opinion to the EPA for the City of Sunnyvale's Cleanwater Program Phase 2 Project on October 5, 2020 (Service file number: 08FBDT00-2020-F-0111) which included activities in and near Sunnyvale West and Moffett Channels.

California Clapper Rail

California clapper rails have been consistently documented in low densities in Guadalupe Slough during the breeding season surveys for the Invasive Spartina Program (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2020, 2021, 2022). The quality of the nesting habitat decreases upstream (i.e., south toward the project area) on Moffett Channel from Guadalupe Slough, as the number of channels and the amount of alkali bulrush and marsh gumplant decreases with distance from the Bay and freshwater vegetation (e.g., tules, common reed) becomes predominant; marsh gumplant is not present in Moffett Channel closer to the proposed project area and tules cover over 50 percent of the marsh. Because California clapper rails typically nest in broader marshes with well-developed tidal channels (conditions that are absent from the proposed project area), they are not expected to nest within the proposed project area.

While nesting isn't likely to occur within the Action Area, California clapper rails may forage in the tule- and common reed-dominated brackish marshes in Guadalupe Slough and Moffett Channel, to the confluence with Sunnyvale West and East Channels, with decreasing probability as the habitat suitability diminishes with declining salinity. As cited in the Draft Environmental Impact Report, California clapper rails have been recorded in marsh habitat in the project area during the nonbreeding season in Moffett Channel and along Guadalupe Slough.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

As cited in the Draft Environmental Impact Report, salt marsh harvest mice have been documented in the vicinity of Pond A4 and suitable habitat for this species occurs immediately adjacent to the proposed project area along the southern edge of Pond A4, within Guadalupe Slough, and in the Sunnyvale Baylands Seasonal Wetland Preserve located east of the Twin Creeks Sports Complex. However, suitable salt marsh habitat is patchy and fragmented within the proposed project area. Salt marsh harvest mice are not expected to occur in coastal brackish marsh dominated by pure stands of cattail and California bulrush along Sunnyvale West Channel and Moffett Channel. Salt marsh harvest mice may be present in tidal and non-tidal brackish marsh immediately adjacent to the proposed project area. The potential for salt marsh harvest mice to occur in the proposed project area is fairly low but cannot be discounted.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the

proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it will not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Habitat

Construction activities will take place within or adjacent to the existing footprints of the Sunnyvale Channels and access road, marginally suitable for foraging rails and mice. Any loss of vegetation on channel banks following bank stabilization activities would be temporary as a native hydroseed mix would be applied to modified channel banks after construction.

Conservation Measures are proposed to reduce habitat degradation downstream along with buffers and construction and species exclusion fencing to reduce the potential for effects outside of the project footprint.

Noise

Existing operations and maintenance of the WPCP and Sunnyvale Channels and human activity near the Sunnyvale Channels provide a baseline level of disturbance, but construction noise will exceed baseline conditions. According to Barber *et al.* (2009), noise levels above 3 A-weighted decibels (dBA) above background levels can result in a 50 percent reduced listening area and 30 percent reduced alerting distance in wildlife while noise levels above 10 dBA above background levels can result in 90 percent reduced alerting distance. The Transportation Noise Control Center (1997) found that noise levels over 80 dBA above background levels caused behavior disruption in foraging, breeding, egg incubation, and rearing of young in various bird species. In a study by Rasmussen *et al.* (2009), lab mice exposed to construction noise levels 70-90 dBA above background levels for ≥ 1 hour/day during gestation led to decreased reproductive efficiency (by decreasing live birth rates and increasing the number of stillborn pups).

Equipment noise and vibration may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual rails and mice to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. The Draft Environmental Impact Report noise analysis concludes that construction noise at 50 feet from the construction site will be 84 Equivalent Sound Levels (L_{eq}) dBA, 76 L_{eq} dBA at 100 feet, 68 L_{eq} dBA at 200 feet, 60 L_{eq} dBA at 400 feet, and 56 L_{eq} dBA at 600 feet using a rate of 8 dBA attenuation rate for each doubling of distance. The City of Sunnyvale used a 7.5 dBA attenuation rate specific to 2020 Cleanwater Program Phase 2 Project consultation. The difference is assumed to be due to the Draft Environmental Impact Report analysis focusing on noise impacts to the developed environment. The Service has used both 6 and 7.5 attenuation rates in consultations depending on the level of development and acoustical barriers between the construction site and the marsh. Given the developed nature of the areas surrounding the sloughs the Service finds a 7.5 dBA attenuation rate appropriate for this consultation. Using a 7.5 dBA attenuation rate, the noise levels would be 76.5 L_{eq} dBA at 100 feet, 69 L_{eq} dBA at 200 feet, 61.5 L_{eq} dBA at 400 feet, and 54 L_{eq} dBA at 800 feet with species experiencing noise disturbance from construction to at least 800 feet from the noise source.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the *Environmental Baseline* and analyzed in consideration of all potential *Cumulative Effects*, will not rise to the level of reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of the species based on the following: (1) effects of construction are mostly limited to temporary increase in noise disturbance; (2) no physical disturbance to suitable nesting habitat will occur for either species and any effects to marginal fragmented foraging habitat will be temporary; and (3) implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures* to minimize adverse effects.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of "take" in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3) Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the EPA so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The EPA has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the EPA (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the EPA must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to

the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: their inherently elusive behavior, their propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, by impairing essential behaviors such as foraging or predator evasion, of all salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails in the salt and brackish marsh habitat within the 100-acre project boundary and 800 feet into the adjacent marsh habitats. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of California clapper rail or salt marsh harvest mouse.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse resulting from implementation of this proposed project have been incorporated into the proposed project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse:

1. All *Conservation Measures*, as described in the proposed project documents and restated here in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the terms and conditions below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implements the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The EPA shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of

the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail from project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the *Description of the Proposed Action* in this biological opinion.

- b. The EPA shall ensure that their applicant immediately notifies the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rail, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.
- c. The EPA and/or their applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
- d. The EPA shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this project.
- e. The EPA and/or their applicant shall ensure any personnel identified as biological monitors or biologists, who are responsible for ensuring compliance with the *Conservation Measures* or other parts of the project which may affect federally-listed species, be Service-approved prior to implementing those activities.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the proposed project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinstate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed Project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed Project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1b, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the California Natural Diversity Data Base (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/California/NaturalDiversityDatabase/Submitting-Data>).

3. The applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the proposed project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
2. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
3. Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Santa Clara Valley Water District's Sunnyvale East and Sunnyvale West Channels Flood Protection Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

(1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;

(2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;

(3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or

(4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

(1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and

(2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to the Service File Number: 2022-0007925-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this consultation.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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